

CARBON FIBER'S SURFACE CHEMISTRY AND SELF-ASSEMBLED INTERPHASE FORMATION IN FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *Carbon fiber, atomic force microscopy, inverse gas chromatography, adhesion mapping, surface energy, toughened interphase, self-assembled interphase*

1 Introduction

Adhesion between carbon fibers and a polymer matrix has been documented to substantially affect mechanical properties of carbon fiber reinforced polymer (CFRP). Adhesion level generally relies on the formation of an interphase between the sized carbon fiber and the polymer matrix and chemical interactions within this interphase. Yet, strong adhesion is not always sought since adverse effects could be resulted, as commonly observed in conventional CFRP systems. However, the authors previously showed that if the interphase could have been toughened by a nanosized reinforcement, synergistic effect of strong adhesion and high fracture toughness of the interphase could maximize certain key properties of the composite and eliminate some common trade-offs in conventional CFRP systems [1].

This paper discusses importance of the carbon fiber surface in contribution to adhesion and subsequently a robust interphase formation by a self-assembled process of the nanosized reinforcement. Model systems are illustrated to demonstrate the concept. Several carbon fiber surfaces created by different levels of surface treatment were quantified and compared among X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS), atomic force microscopy (AFM), and inverse gas chromatography (IGC). Effects of surface chemistry on adhesion between the fiber and polymer matrix were documented by interlaminar shear strength (IFSS) of single fibers and interlaminar shear test (ILSS) of CFRP. Effects of the reinforced interphase on the selected carbon

fiber composite's performance were illustrated by tensile and open-hole tension (OHT) strengths.

2 Materials and Methods

2.1 Materials

A model PAN-based carbon fiber, viz. C0, having intermediate modulus was made by Toray Industries, Inc. (Japan). The fiber was oxidized by a wet chemistry method using two different oxidizing agents A and B. Four oxidization levels per agent were performed. Table 1 summarizes the virgin fiber (control) and resulting oxidized fibers studied in the present paper.

A model epoxy resin system was formulated by Toray Composites (America) Inc. for composite tests. The resin contained a mixture of epoxies, a curing agent, a migrating agent and a type of nanoparticles.

2.2 Methods

2.2.1. Surface topography. A JEOL 7500F SEM equipped with a gentle beam technology was used to examine and compare nanostructures on the fiber surfaces. Individual fibers were cut into short lengths and suspended in methanol by sonication. A small drop of solution was placed on a TEM grid on a filter paper. The TEM grid was removed after the solvent was evaporated and glued onto an aluminium stud. No coating was applied to the short fibers to preserve surface nanostructures. Images were taken at 500V and a working distance between 2-3 mm.

2.2.2. *Surface chemistry mapping.* A Witec Alpha300 equipped with a digital pulse forced mode (AFM-DPFM) from University of Idaho (Moscow, Idaho) was used to map adhesion forces between a tip and a location on the carbon fiber surface [2]. Two types of AFM tip with a force constant of 0.021 N/m and 0.074 N/m (Nanosensors PointProbes, PPP-CONTR) were used to map surface of carbon fibers A and B, respectively. Typical settings were set point of 0.5V, scan rate of 0.6 lines/s, 256 x 1024 pixels for 0.5 x 5 um, and PFM frequency of 1 kHz.

An inverse gas chromatography (IGC) from Surface Measurement Systems Ltd. (London, UK) was used to obtain dispersive surface energy and BET surface area of the fibers [3]. Each fiber was cut into a length of about 5 mm and packed into a glass column up to 2 g of fibers. The column was preconditioned at 120 °C for 2 hr before taking measurements.

2.2.3. *Mechanical tests.* Adhesion tests were carried out by a single fiber fragmentation test [2] and short beam shear (ASTM D-2344). Test coupons of the latter test were fabricated by a resin infusion method.

Tensile and open-hole tension tests were carried out according to ASTM D 3039 on 6-ply unidirectional zero degree and ASTM D 5766 on 8-ply quasi-isotropic layups, respectively. The prepregs were made by a hot-melt process using heat and pressure. Fiber area weight (FAW) and resin content were 190 g/m² and 35 %. Fiber volume was about 55 %. Panels were cured in an autoclave at 180 °C for 2 hr with a ramp rate of 1.7 °C/min and a pressure of 0.59 MPa.

3 Results and discussion

3.1. Surface topography. The virgin fiber C0 was surface treated by oxidizing agents A, B using a wet chemistry method. Four different oxidization levels (conditions 1-4) per oxidizing agent were obtained. XPS was used to quantify the ratio of oxygen to carbon element (O/C). Generally, the more aggressive surface treatment condition (i.e., strength) leads to the higher O/C ratio. Table 1 shows that normalized O/C ratio to the virgin fiber

C0 increases rapidly for mild conditions and reached a plateau after 3rd condition, and 2nd condition with oxidizing agents A and B, respectively.

Fig. 1 illustrates examples of carbon fiber A's surfaces obtained from SEM. As shown, long and fat ribbons of the control (fiber C0) started to get shorter and thinner after condition #2 (fiber A2), indicating the fiber surface was effectively oxidized by the agent A. As more harsh conditions were applied these ribbons became very short but more uniform (fibers A3-A4). As a result, the fiber surface became flatter.

Similar surface topography could be observed for B fibers in Fig. 2. After condition #2 the fiber started to show significant surface damages (fiber B3). Up to condition #4 the fiber surface started to peel off (fiber B4). Note that some loose structures on the fiber surface, especially for fibers A3-A4, and B3-B4, might have been removed during sample preparation by sonication in methanol.

Comparing SEM images and O/C ratio, one could rationalize that surface damages could contribute to the plateaus of O/C presented in Table 1.

3.2. Surface chemistry

3.2.1. AFM. Atomic force microscopy equipped with a pulse force mode (AFM-PFM) was interested to map the distribution of oxygen groups on the fiber surfaces as well as to quantify surface roughness observed by SEM images. AFM-PFM technique has been used extensively to map a flat surface chemistry by quantifying adhesion forces between a tip and an area on the surface beneath the tip. To date, the authors have demonstrated that this technique could be applied to a curve surface such as carbon fibers [2]. Yet, extreme care should be taken not only on sample preparation but also operation parameters so that the average adhesion per scanned area size could be compared among different fiber surfaces.

Fig. 3 compares representative adhesion maps from different oxidization levels using the agent A in addition to topography maps. Optimal scan size was 0.5 um x 5 um to minimize curvature effect on the largest possible area. Each fiber without

sonication in methanol was taped on a silicon wafer individually and without touching one another to avoid vibrations during scanning. Going from the control to fiber A2 similar topography and adhesion map were observed. Yet, from condition #3 the surface appeared a little flatter and adhesion map became grainier. The opposite was true for condition #4. While topography appeared to have some transition from a bumpy surface to a smoother surface and vice versa, adhesion maps for all conditions were found to be uniform, implying that uniform distribution of surface groups on these fibers, i.e., very good control of surface treatment with the agent A. Similar trends could be observed for surface treatment with the agent B. As shown in Fig. 4, however, more dramatic surface changes were found. Note that a softer cantilever was used for B fibers. This affects adhesion significantly, but a little to none to topography.

Quantifying surface topography change by both average (Ra) and root-mean-square (RMS) surface roughness and adhesion were performed. Though, a relatively small number of good images of at least 5 on multiple individual fibers was used, these averages could give a rough idea how the surface changed after each surface treatment condition. For better statistically meaningful averages, the sample size should have been much larger. The summaries are presented in Figs. 5-6. The average surface roughness values in Fig. 5 corroborate observations from SEM images (Figs. 1-2) and AFM topography images (Figs. 3-4). Though no BET surface area of B fibers was taken, that of A fibers seems to correlate well with surface roughness by AFM. A higher surface roughness by the agent B for conditions, #3, #4 than #2 could be due to where the scanned areas on the fibers were taken place. As observed from SEM images, these conditions damaged surface greatly, especially the latter could cause the outer layer to peel off.

3.2.2. *IGC*. Inverse gas chromatography was interested to complement the traditional XPS or potentially to replace XPS as it is capable of sampling a much larger size of carbon fibers. Surface chemistry as well as roughness of a surface could be represented by surface energy and acid/base characteristics of the surface and BET surface area. Recently, Surface Measurement

Systems Ltd. (London, UK) has advanced IGC with an automatic probe injection system, high injection volumes and ease of data analyses. Figs. 7 and 8 correlate dispersive surface energy at 60 °C to O/C ratio for A and B fibers, respectively. It was noticed that the precondition at 120 °C for 2 hr effectively removed physisorbed species such as water, CO, CO₂ [4-5], leading to a relatively clean surface thus higher surface energy than without precondition. In addition, for highly oxidized fiber surface probe gases were found to be more difficult to traverse through the column packed with short fibers. Hence, higher column temperature would be needed. Yet, surface energy in most cases linearly decreasingly proportional to temperature. For the purpose of this paper one column up to 2 g of fiber per fiber type was used. Dispersive component of surface energy, or dispersive energy probed by a series of alkane gases was of interest. For comparison among surfaces a stable dispersive energy at 60 °C was found. Similar to other methods, IGC also had some difficulty probing the surface at high O/C ratios at which surface damages extensively occurred. Therefore, no data was available for fiber B4 at condition #4 at 60 °C. Interesting, surface energy continued to increase though other techniques to probe surface chemistry such as XPS approaching a plateau. This could be because the probe gas molecules can penetrate the surface deeper beyond a location that other methods could reach. BET surface area from fibers A corroborated this finding. In addition, since a much larger sample size was used, the average dispersive energies represented surface chemistry of hundreds of thousands of fibers versus one or more fibers from other techniques.

3.3. Adhesion versus surface topography and chemistry

Average values of adhesion in Fig. 6 show a similar tendency as surface roughness versus O/C ratio. Adhesion increased with increasing O/C ratio and reached a plateau once significant surface damages started to play a role. Adhesion was higher for B fibers compared to A fibers due to softer cantilever used. At higher surface damages, i.e., fibers A4 and B3-B4, adhesion was decreased. These measurements, depending on the location on the fiber, could represent adhesion between the tip and a subsurface underneath the oxidized outer layer.

Figs. 7 and 8 also compare adhesion by IFSS vs. ILSS for fibers A and B, respectively. ILSS shows a similar trend as AFM adhesion. Yet, IFSS on the other hand showed a great fluctuation versus O/C ratio at harsh conditions. Since the measurement came from a small sample size of single fibers, it was expected that some fibers or some fiber lengths, which were weaker than others, could be selected for the test. In addition, the highly oxidized outermost layer of these fibers while adhered well to the polymer matrix could be peeled off. Since this layer was not strongly bound to the core, IFSS could be lower. ILSS, on the other hand, with a large fiber volume (~50%) provided a better statistically meaningful average. Note that a large fiber volume could cause other complications, yet the discussion is beyond the scope of this paper.

From AFM, IFSS, ILSS observations, one can conclude that the contribution of surface chemistry to adhesion between a fiber and the polymer matrix play a more important role under mild surface treatment conditions at which oxygen content increased without penalizing much surface damages. However, at a certain level of surface treatment it is difficult to discount the contribution of surface damages hence roughness. Under harsh conditions, contribution from both surface roughness and surface chemistry could be similar. Yet, adhesion could be lower as the outermost layer while adhered strongly to the polymer matrix was weakly bonded to the core and skinned off more easily.

3.4. Self-assembled toughened interphase (SATI)
Surface chemistry and surface topography play a unique role in creating an interphase between a fiber and a polymer matrix. The requirement for the fiber surface is to have an optimal balance of O/C ratio and surface roughness. Yet, there should be a high enough O/C ratio so that a sizing material could be bonded to the oxygen functional groups on the surface on one end and functional groups of the polymer matrix on the other end. To illustrate the importance of fiber surface chemistry and topography on composite's properties, carbon fiber B2 was selected. A proprietary sizing material was coated on the fiber. A model aerospace grade resin was formulated with a migrating agent and a type of nanoparticles. The resin was impregnated on the

sized fiber bed to create unidirectional (UD) prepreg. An interphase having the nanomaterial localized in the vicinity of the fibers formed by a self-assembled process upon curing was illustrated in Fig. 9. The interphase formation was confirmed by SEM images in Fig. 10 from cross-section and fiber surface after fracture. As shown, an interphase might exist in both cases. However, it could not be detected from the control but the modified with a uniform layer of the nanomaterial around the fiber. The modified also showed cohesive failure of the resin in the nanomaterial layer. Without a good design and understanding of carbon fiber surface, such an interphase would not have been achieved. Once the interphase was formed successfully, significant improvements of tensile strength and open-hole tension were achieved 16% and 50% compared to the control, respectively.

4 Conclusions

This paper illustrates the importance of carbon fiber surface chemistry and topography in designing a high performance composite. As illustrated, surface treatment of carbon fiber plays a significant role. While XPS has been used exclusively to document the quality of a surface treatment, recent advanced developments of SEM, AFM, and IGC could complement XPS. By utilizing one of more of these tools, one could select the right condition for a surface treatment. Visual inspection by SEM and AFM are recommended to complement XPS and/or IGC, especially at harsh conditions. While all presented techniques were suitable to document fiber surfaces with low to moderate surface damages and showed similar trends, ILSS and IGC could be more effective tools with excessive damages.

Once the right carbon surface could be prepared, a reinforced interphase by nanomaterials could be made and controlled well. Subsequently, property trade-offs commonly observed in CFRP could be minimized; hence significant improvement on performance envelop could be made possible.

Fig. 1 – SEM images of A fibers oxidized by the agent A versus the virgin fiber (control). Scale bar is 100 nm.

Fig. 2 – SEM images of B fibers oxidized by the agent B versus the virgin fiber (control). Scale bar is 100 nm.

Fig. 3 – AFM images of A fibers oxidized by the agent A versus the virgin fiber (control). For each set the left image is topography (nm) and the right image is adhesion map (nN). Spring constant is 0.21 N/m. Image size is 0.5 μ m x 5 μ m.

Fig. 4 – AFM images of B fibers oxidized by the agent B versus the virgin fiber (control). For each set the left image is topography (nm) and the right image is adhesion map (nN). Spring constant is 0.074 N/m. Image size is 0.5 μ m x 5 μ m.

Table 1 – Carbon fibers used in the present study

Oxidizing agent	Fiber #	Surface treatment		Normalized O/C [XPS data]
		Condition No.	Relative strength	
-	C0	-	-	1
A	A1	1	1	3
	A2	2	3.5	4
	A3	3	10	10
	A4	4	35	12
B	B1	1	13.5	7
	B2	2	27	10
	B3	3	40	11
	B4	4	135	12

Fig. 5 – Surface roughness by AFM. Average value of 5 images as shown in Figs. 3-4 (0.5 μ m x 5 μ m) are shown. Solid lines project estimated trends.

Fig. 6 – Adhesion force between an AFM tip and a fiber surface. Average value of 5 images as shown in Figs. 3-4 is shown. Solid lines project estimated trends.

Fig. 7 – Quantitative measurements of surface chemistry and BET surface area versus O/C ratio by XPS for A fibers and control. Solid lines project estimated trends. The enclosed area by dash line indicates optimal surface treatment conditions.

Fig. 8 – Quantitative measurements of surface chemistry and BET surface area versus O/C ratio by XPS for B fibers and control. Solid lines project estimated trends. The enclosed area by dash line indicates optimal surface treatment conditions.

1st layer: functional group + sizing + resin component

2nd layer: nanoparticle + resin component

Fig. 9 – Schematic of a toughened interphase formed in CFRP after cured by a self-assembled toughened interphase (SATI) process. (1) Migrating agent, (2) Nanomaterial, (3) Fiber, (4) Resin. Drawing is not to scale.

Fig. 10 – SEM images shows a reinforced interphase formation by SATI process. Each set includes cross-section view and fiber surface view after fractured.

References

- [1] F.N. Nguyen, A. Haro, K. Yoshioka, “Maximizing Fiber-To-Composite Strength Translation with a Nanomaterial-Reinforced Interphase”, *SAMPE TECH*, South Carolina October 2012
- [2] F.N. Nguyen, Y. Nakayama, D. Kobayashi, T. Kamae, K. Yoshioka, “Carbon fiber’s surface and its effects on an interphase formation for ultimate adhesion-related performances”, *SAMPE*, Baltimore May 2012
- [3] D.J. Burnett, J. Khoo, “Surface energy heterogeneity of carbon fibers-effects of heat treatment and sizing”, *SAMPE*, Baltimore May 2012
- [4] L.T., Drzal, “The surface composition and energetics of type A graphite fibers”, *Carbon*, Vol. 15, pp. 129-138, 1977
- [5] L.T., Drzal, J.A., Mescher, D.L. Hall, “The surface composition and energetics of type HM graphite fibers”, *Carbon*, Vol. 17, 375 (1979)